

Dear study participants,

Our research group at <blinded> is currently investigating **mobile device theft** and what happens when someone steals your phone. You booked an interview slot with us and we are thus required to ask for your **consent for participation** in our study. The following gives an overview of the study, the procedure, the data collected, confidentiality, and your rights. Please read everything carefully and let us know if you have any questions. If you don't have any questions or we have answered your questions sufficiently, please answer the questions below according to your preference.

By giving your consent below, you confirm that

- you are at least 18 years old

- you have read or have been read this declaration of consent and information on data protection

Study name Understanding End-User Preparation, Reaction, and Advice-Seeking Behavior During Mobile Device Theft Incidents

<blinded> | E-Mail: <blinded>

Data Protection Officer: E-Mail: <blinded>

Study goal and purposes of data processing The aim of our project is to understand what happens when someone steals your phone. We do this by means of an interview study in which we will ask you some general questions regarding stolen smartphones and privacy. Then we will do some thought experiments, where you will be given scenarios based on which we will ask you questions.

Data categories We will collect video and audio tracks in Zoom. The video track will be deleted immediately after the interview. The audio track of the conversation will be recorded for later evaluation in transcribed form. The audio recordings will be deleted after transcription.

We will gather quantitative behavioral data on app usage to understand how people interact with the app. Additionally, we will collect qualitative data to gain insights into the specific apps that users engage with. Furthermore, demographic information of age and gender will be collected, as well as open-ended responses regarding app and study evaluation.

Methods The study consists of an approximately 60-minute-long interview over Zoom with some general questions about what happens when someone steals your phone, some scenario-based thought experiments based on privacy of commonly used apps. It is important to note that there are no right or wrong answers for this study. We are only interested in your individual perspective and opinion.

Content Warning In this interview, we will talk about device theft and strategies for mitigating and recovering from the impact of device theft. We understand that talking about these topics may be uncomfortable for you. We would like to reassure you the following:

- **You will be free to terminate the interview at any time without giving reasons.**
- **We will not show pictures/videos of any kind.**
- **The contexts provided in the interview will be completely fictional in nature.**
- **If you feel uncomfortable with this topic, you are free to not participate in this study.**

Confidentiality

Storage location: Potential threats to the confidentiality of this study are minimized by securing all data on our devices issued by our research institution and storing it in a secure cloud storage system hosted by our research institute. Only authorized researchers will have access to this data.

The consent for this study will be collected using the Qualtrics questionnaire software. This data will be stored on Qualtrics servers and will only be accessible via password-protected user accounts. All data downloaded from Qualtrics servers will be stored in a secure cloud storage system hosted by our research institution.

If you agree, we may use a third-party transcription and/or translation service.

Your name and personal identification information will be stored only for the purpose of enabling your participation and on this consent form to document your consent. This data will not be kept together with your study data and will be deleted immediately after your participation.

Results from this study may be presented at conferences, published in scientific journals or shared with scientific institutions upon request. As data is anonymous, it is not possible to draw any conclusions about your identity.

Storage duration: Anonymized data and study documents can be kept for a period of at least 10 years.

Your rights

You have the right to information, correction, deletion, restriction of processing, and data portability, as well as a right of appeal to a supervisory authority of your choice.

Your participation is voluntary. If you decide to participate, you can cancel your participation at any time and revoke this declaration of consent with effect for the future. In this case, we will also delete all data collected from you until then. Please note that after completion of the study, all data will be anonymized, and therefore, deletion of your data is no longer possible from this point on.

If you decide to end your participation, if you have any questions, concerns, or complaints, or if you wish to report a violation related to the study, please contact the person(s) responsible for this study.

This study was reviewed in accordance with <blinded> ERB guidelines for research involving human subjects

Thank you very much in advance for your participation in this study.

- **Yes**, I consent to **participate** in this survey.
- **No**, I **do not** consent to **participate** in this survey.

I consent to the **usage of my data** of this study in a **publication** about this topic by the researchers.

- Yes, I consent.
- No, I do not consent.

I consent the usage of **anonymous citations** from my interview in the **publication** about this topic.

- Yes, I consent.
- No, I do not consent.
- I consent with the following terms: _____

I consent to the **sharing** of my **anonymized data** from this study to a scientific institute upon request.

- Yes, I consent
- No, I do not consent
- I consent with the following terms: _____

I have **read and understood the content warning** and understand that I can **terminate the interview** at any time without stating any reason.

- Yes, I have.
- No, I have not.

I **consent** that the interview will be **recorded** and used for analysis by members of the research institution.

- Yes, I consent.
- No, I do not consent.

I **consent** to the **transcription** of the audio recording by a third party.

- Yes, I consent.
- No, I do not consent.
- I consent with the following terms: _____

I **consent** to the **translation** of the transcription by a third party.

- Yes, I consent.
- No, I do not consent.
- I consent with the following terms: _____